

A New Synthesis of Quinazolines. Part I.

BY TARAPADA BHATTACHARYYA, PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND
JNANENDRA NATH RAY.

Phosphoric oxide induces the reaction between ethyl acetoacetate and phenols to give γ -pyrones (*cf.* Petschek and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2014). It suggested to the present authors that acetyl urethane $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHCOOC}_2\text{H}_5$ which presents a unique similarity to acetoacetic ester, should also condense with amines under the influence of phosphoric oxide to give oxyquinazolines (I) or the isomeric substance (II).

For the preparation of quinazolines various methods have been employed (*cf.* Anschutz, Schmidt and Greiffenberg, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3480; also Bogert and collaborators, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 649, 1305, 1327; 1906, 28, 94, 207, 884, 1449; *cf.* also Bischler and Lang, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 282; Niementowski, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, (ii), 51, 546; *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1360; *Annalen*, 1877, 184, 349; *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1850, etc.) none of which has the advantage over the one proposed above.

An isolated attempt to condense amines with acetyl urethane is recorded by Young (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 361). This investigator attempted to condense ammonia and amines with acetyl urethane without any condensing agent and was only able to isolate phenyl acetyl carbamide and a trace of acetanilide in the condensation with aniline. Therefore it was deemed advisable to study this reaction with amines under the influence of the condensing agent which one

of us successfully employed before in similar reactions (*cf.* Sen and Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 646; De and Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 541).

The condition chosen for the reaction was very similar to that of De and Rây (*loc. cit.*). Two products were isolated, one crystallised out from the xylene employed as a diluent in the reaction, and another substance was obtained after neutralisation of the phosphoric acid solution obtained by decomposing the reaction product with ice. This latter substance was basic and the non-basic product from xylene was found to be a carbamide derivative. The latter reaction can take place either as—

+ EtOH, to give a carbamide,

to give an amidine.

Both products are formed but IV is distinctly basic in character and also unstable. Using a large excess of phosphoric oxide quinazolines are isolated from *m*-toluidine and *m*-anisidine. But the quinazolines may have either the structure I or II as the isolation of intermediates III and IV strongly suggests. To ascertain whether the quinazolines should be formulated as I or II, we condensed *m*-acetotoluidide and urethane.

In the above reaction, the product can only be a 4-oxyquinazoline and we found that this product was identical with that we obtained from acetyl urethane and *m*-toluidine. Therefore we concluded that the quinazolines were really 4-oxy compounds instead of the isomeric 2-oxy derivatives, and in this reaction the course is parallel to that depicted by Simonis (*loc. cit.*) in his γ -chromone synthesis.

Having found the optimum conditions for the reaction we have reacted a number of acylamines with urethane and obtained the

corresponding quinazolines. The procedure adopted has essentially been the same as that of De and Rây in their investigation of the alleged constitution of vasicine (*loc. cit.*)

These quinazolines easily methylate with methyl iodide and potassium hydroxide in alcohol and we agree with Bogert and Seil (*loc. cit.*) in assigning a $N\text{-CH}_3$ structure to the methylated derivatives.

This is also in harmony with some further work that has since been done by one of us.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Acetyl urethane with m-Toluidine: Formation of
(a) *Acetyl m-tolyl carbamide* $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NHCO} \cdot \text{NHCO} \cdot \text{CH}_3$ and

(b) *2:7-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline* (Formula I, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$).

(a) Acetyl urethane (8 g.), *m*-toluidine (6 g.) and dry xylene (25 c. c.) were gradually treated with phosphoric oxide (10-12 g.) with stirring at $125^\circ\text{-}135^\circ$ for 3 hours. Xylene was decanted off from the sticky product and furnished a crystalline substance on cooling. This was recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 123° (yield 3.5 gm.). (Found : N, 14.56. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent.)

(b) The above experiment was repeated with 35 gms. of phosphoric oxide. The xylene solution furnished almost nothing. The sticky mass left in the vessel was decomposed with ice water and filtered from a little undissolved impurity. The aqueous solution was neutralised with aqueous sodium hydroxide till the solution remained only slightly acidic. A voluminous mass of a colourless substance separated which was collected and purified by recrystallisation from hot alcohol (twice); m. p. 244° . (Found : N, 16.01. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.) This substance did not depress the m. p. of the product obtained from acetyl *m*-toluidide and urethane and is obviously (b) of the title of this section.

Condensation of m-Anisidine with Acetyl urethane: Preparation of
(c) *m-Methoxyphenyl acetyl carbamide* and (d) *2-Methyl-7-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline* (Formula I, $\text{R} = \text{OCH}_3$).

(c) An intimate mixture of urethane (7 g.), *m*-anisidine (5 g.) and phosphoric oxide (10 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) was heated as in the previous experiment, when from the cold xylene solution, long colourless needles of (c) separated out; m.p. 200°, after recrystallisation from spirit. (Found: N, 13.27. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.46 per cent.)

(d) In the above experiment when 25 gms. of phosphoric oxide were used, the aqueous solution, obtained after decomposition of the product with crushed ice, gave on neutralisation a substance which melted at 257° after repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 14.84. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.73 per cent.)

Condensation of Acetyl Urethane and Aniline: Formation of (e) Acetyl Phenyl Carbamide and (f) Compound (IV).—(e) Using a mixture of acetyl urethane (7 g.), aniline (5 g.), phosphoric oxide (10 g.) and xylene (20 c.c.), we obtained in the usual manner, from the xylene solution compound (e). Crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 183° (*cf.* Walther and Wlodkowski, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, (ii), 59 266, who give 183-184°). (Found: N, 15.73. $C_9H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 15.92 per cent.)

(f) The reaction product, after xylene had been decanted off in the above experiment, was dissolved in water, the aqueous solution was cooled in ice and basified. The separated solid crystallised from alcohol. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.)

Condensation of Acetyl Urethane with o-Toluidine: Formation of Acetyl o-tolylurea.—When acetyl urethane (7 g.), *o*-toluidine (5 g.), phosphoric oxide (12 g.) and xylene (20 c.c.) were heated at 130°-140° for 3 hours, from the decanted xylene solution was isolated the above compound. It was recrystallised from alcohol in slender needles, m.p. 166°. Walther and Wlodkowski (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 168°. (Found: N, 14.62. Calc. N, 14.58 per cent.) No quinazoline could be isolated in this case in a pure state. Similarly when the above condensation was done with (i) *m*-asym-xylidine, (ii) *o*-phenetidine, (iii) *o*-anisidine, carbamides were isolated but not the amidines or quinazolines.

(i) The acetyl carbamide from *m*-asym-xylidine, m.p. 194°. (Found: N, 13.37. Calc. N, 13.59 per cent.)

(ii) The acetyl carbamide from *o*-phenetidine was *m*-ethoxyphenyl acetyl carbamide, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 12.83. Calc. N, 12.61 per cent.)

(iii) *o*-Methoxyphenyl acetyl carbamide from *o*-anisidine, m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 13.21. Calc. N, 13.46 per cent.)

Condensation of Acetanilide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Methyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—Acetanilide (9 g.), urethane (8 g.), was thoroughly ground together, heated with xylene (30 c.c.), and phosphoric oxide (35 g.) was gradually introduced into the mixture kept boiling at 145°-150° (bath temperature) for 6 hours. The product was cooled and water introduced with care. The aqueous solution, well freed from the xylene layer, was further cooled and treated with a strong solution of sodium hydroxide till the resulting solution was only slightly acidic. The separated precipitate, well washed with water, was crystallised from hot alcohol, m.p. 231° (yield, 2.5 g.) (Found: C, 67.05; H, 5.6; N, 17.14. $C_9H_8ON_2$ requires C, 67.50; H, 5.0; N, 17.50 per cent.) Bogert and Gotthelf (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, **22**, 522) give the m.p. 232-233°.

2:3-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—The above substance (0.8 g.) m.p. 231° was dissolved in 10 c.c. of 2.8 per cent. solution of sodium hydroxide in methyl alcohol and refluxed with 0.8 c.c. of methyl iodide for three hours. On evaporation and washing the residue with dilute alkali and water, a substance was obtained which crystallised in fine long needles, m.p. 112°-113°: Bogert and Gotthelf (*loc.cit.*) give 110°-111°. (Found: N, 15.72. Calc. N, 16.08 per cent.)

Condensation of m-Acetotoluidide with Urethane: Formation of 2:7-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—*m*-Acetotoluidide (8 g.), urethane (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) and xylene (25 c.c.) were heated at 140°-150° (bath temperature) for 6 hours. The product after decomposition with water was isolated as usual from the aqueous solution by neutralisation and was crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 2 g.). (Found: N, 16.01. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.) The substance melted alone, or when mixed with the product from *m*-toluidine and acetyl urethane, at 244°.

Condensation of p-Acetotoluidide with Urethane: Formation of 2:6-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—*p*-Acetotoluidide (8 g.), urethane (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) and xylene (25 c.c.) were heated at 140°-150° for 6 hours. The product was isolated as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol (twice). Yield 1.5 g.; m.p. 240°. The substance, like all the members of this series, dissolves in dilute acids and alkali (*cf.* Bischler and Muntemdam, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 729). (Found: N, 16.34. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.)

The *picrate* of the above quinazoline was prepared in alcoholic solution in the usual manner and crystallised from dilute alcohol. Yellowish crystals, m.p. 196-198°.

Condensation of Aceto-o-toluidide with Urethane: Formation of 2:8-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—Interaction of aceto-*o*-toluidide (9 g.), urethane (7 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) at 140°-150° for 6 hours, furnished the substance and was isolated in the usual manner. The yield of the recrystallised product from dilute alcohol was 2 g.; m.p. 240°. The substance is very soluble in acids, alkali and alcohol. (Found: N, 15.72. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.). *Picrate*, m.p. 164°.

2:3:8-Trimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—One g. of the above quinazoline dissolved in 10 c.c. of 2.8% solution of potassium hydroxide in methyl alcohol was refluxed with 0.7 c.c. of methyl iodide for 3 hours. The residue after the evaporation of the solvent was washed with dilute alkali and water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in thick plates, m.p. 107°. The substance was now insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 14.88. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.88 per cent.).

Condensation of Aceto-m-asym-xylylidide with Urethane: Formation of 2:6:8-Trimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.

Aceto-*m*-xylylidide (8 g.), urethane (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were heated for 6 hours at 145-155°. The product after isolation by the usual method crystallised from hot absolute alcohol (yield, 3 g.), m.p. 266° (*cf.* Bamberger and Weller, *J.pr. Chem.*, 1898, (ii) 58 333 give m.p. 271°). (Found: N, 14.88. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.86 per cent.). It formed a *picrate*, m.p. 197°.

2:3:6:8-Tetramethyl-4-quinazolone.—*2:6:8-Trimethylquinazolone* gives, on methylation in dilute alkali solution with methyl iodide, the above compound, m.p. 146° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 13.69. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

2:6:8-Trimethyl-3-ethyl-4-quinazolone was prepared similarly to the tetramethyl compound using ethyl iodide in the place of methyl iodide; m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 13.09. $C_{13}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 12.96 per cent.). The substance is soluble in acids but insoluble in alkalis.

Condensation of Aceto-p-anisidide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Methyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline.

Aceto-*p*-anisidide (8 g.), urethane (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were heated for 6 hours at 140°-150°. The product was isolated in the usual manner. It crystallised from absolute alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 257° (yield, 3 g.). The substance is very easily soluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 14.65. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires

N, 14.73 per cent.). The *N*-methyl derivative of the compound, *i.e.*, 2:3-dimethyl-6-methoxy-4-quinazolone was prepared by methylation with methyl iodide in alkali, m.p. 131°. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.72 per cent.).

Condensation of Aceto-o-anisidide with Urethane.

2-Methyl-8-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline was prepared from aceto-o-anisidide (8 g.), urethane (7 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) at 140°-150° for 5 hours. The product isolated in the usual manner was purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 243°; yield, 2 g. (Found: N, 14.55. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.73 per cent.).

Methylation in the usual manner furnished 2:3-dimethyl-8-methoxy-4-quinazolone.

Condensation of Aceto-p-phenetidide with Urethane: 2-Methyl-6-ethoxy-4-oxyquinazoline, melting at at 220°, was isolated in good yield from the above constituents after interaction in the usual manner. The substance, when crystallised from alcohol has a slight greenish tinge. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 6.07; N, 13.74. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 64.7; H, 5.88 N, 13.72 per cent.). 2:3-Dimethyl-6-ethoxy-4-oxyquinazoline was prepared by methylation of the compound, m.p. 220°. The substance crystallised in stout prisms with a slight yellowish tinge; m.p. 148° (Found: N, 12.94. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.84 per cent.).

Condensation of Aceto-o-phenetidide and Urethane: Formation of 1-Methyl-8-ethoxy-4-oxyquinazoline.

The above substance was prepared from aceto-o-phenetidide, urethane and phosphoric oxide. The reaction product was decomposed with water and the substance isolated from the aqueous solution in the usual manner. It crystallised from alcohol in slender needles, m.p. 225°. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.72 per cent.).

Condensation of Aceto-a-naphthalide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Methyl-7:8-benzo-4-oxyquinazoline.

1.5 G. of the above substance was isolated in the usual manner from aceto-a-naphthalide (5 g.), urethane (5 g.), phosphoric oxide (30 g.) and xylene (20 c.c.) after heating at 150°-160° for 6 hours. The substance crystallises from alcohol in fibrous needles with a slight yellow tinge. m.p. 322°. It is easily soluble in pyridine and dilute alkali. (Found: N, 13.12. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

Condensation of Aceto- β -naphthalide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Methyl-5:6-benzo-4-oxyquinazoline.

Aceto- β -naphthalide (8 g.), urethane (8 g.) phosphoric oxide (35 g.) and xylene (25 c.c.) were used in this reaction. The product was isolated by adding water to the reaction mixture when the quinazoline came down. The substance is feebly basic and hence the acidic aqueous solution needs no neutralisation for its isolation. The substance was crystallised from pyridine (yield, 3 g.) in cottony needles, m.p. 29.5°. It is easily soluble in alkali. (Found: N, 13.20. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

The *N*-methyl derivative was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 156°. (Found: N, 12.37. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent.).

Condensation of Benzanilide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Phenyl-4-oxyquinazoline.

Benzanilide (9 g.), urethane (10 g.) and phosphoric oxide (40 g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) when heated at 175°-190° (bath temperature) for 6 hours furnished the product after usual treatment. The yield was about 2 g. The substance crystallised from alcohol in pale greenish needles, m.p. 223° (*cf.* Bischler and Lang, *Ber.*, 1898, 29, 279, who give m.p. 223-225°). (Found: N, 12.17. $C_{14}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 12.6 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-quinazolone was obtained by the methylation of the foregoing substance in the usual manner; m.p. 133°. (Korner, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1887, (ii) 36, 155, gives 131°). (Found: N, 11.48. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 11.86 per cent.).

Condensation of Propionanilide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Ethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.

Propionanilide (9 g.), urethane (8 g.), and phosphoric oxide (35 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) at a temperature of 140-150° gave nearly 4 g. of the above compound. The substance crystallises in fine long needles and melts at 227-228° (*cf.* Niementowski, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, (ii) 51, 564, who gives 225°). (Found: C, 68.80; H, 6.00; N, 16.06. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires C, 68.94; H, 5.75; N, 16.09 per cent.). Methylation in the usual manner gave 2-ethyl-3-methyl-4-quinazolone; stout needles, m.p. 121° (*cf.* Gotthelf, *loc. cit.*, who gives m.p. 121°) (Found: N, 14.74. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.90 per cent.).

*Condensation of Propion-*o*-toluidide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Ethyl-8-methyl-4-oxyquinazolone.*

Propion-*o*-toluidide (7 g.), urethane (6 g.) and phosphoric oxide (30 g.) in xylene (20 c.c.) were heated at 145°-155° for 5 hours. The yield was nearly 2.5 g. and the substance crystallised from alcohol in pale brownish needles, m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 14.67. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

Condensation of Propion-p-toluidide with Urethane: Formation of 2-Ethyl-6-methyl-4-oxoquinazoline.

The proportion of the ingredients were as follows: Propion-*p*-toluidide (9 g.), urethane (8 g.), phosphoric oxide (35 g.) and xylene (25 c.c.). The reaction was carried out at 145°-155°. The yield was nearly 3.5 g. The substance crystallises in fine needles, m.p. 227°. (Found: N, 14.73. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

2-Ethyl-3:6-dimethyl-4-quinazolone was obtained by the methylation of the foregoing substance. It crystallised in plates from alcohol, m.p. 111°. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

Our thanks are due to Sir P. C. Ráy for his kind interest during this investigation.

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA,
AND CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
THE UNIVERSITY, LAHORE.

Received February 4, 1929.

